

AGE CRISES IN PSYCHOLOGY AND THE STATE OF THEIR STUDY

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Abstract. *The concept of age crisis in psychology has attracted a lot of attention in recent years and has been the cause of intense debate among researchers. Age crises refer to periods of turmoil and introspection that people experience at various stages of their lives, often triggered by major life events or milestones. This article is aimed at an in-depth study of age crises in psychology, their various types, causes and consequences, as well as the current state of research in this field.*

Keywords: *age crises, periods, mental aspects, cognitive tasks, characterization, emotional communication*

Introduction: There are different ways of classifying age periods in psychology. This approach to the study of the human personality from different points of view and illuminates the nature of this problem in different ways. It is known that each period is distinguished by its important life conditions, needs and activities, its own contradictions, the qualitative features of its psyche and the formation of new psychologically characteristic qualities. Each period is prepared by the period before it and serves as a basis for its formation and, in turn, the emergence of the period after it. At this point, it is appropriate to emphasize the theories of classification of age periods existing in psychology. It includes the theory of mind of the Swiss psychologist J. Piaget, the functions of mind and its periods. The main tasks of intelligence are adaptation and habituation, and this is its permanent set of tasks.

The author classifies the child's intelligence into the following stages of mental development: 1) sensorimotor intelligence - from birth to 2 years; 2) the period of reflection before the operation - from 2 to 7 years; 3) the period of specific operations - from 7, 8 years - to 11, 12 years; 4) period of official operations.

The French psychologist A. Vallon divides age periods into the following stages:

1) the period of the fetus in the mother's womb; 2) period of impulsive action - from birth to 6 months; 3) period of feeling (emotional) - from 6 months to 1 year; 4) sensorimotor (coordination of perception and movement) period - from 1 to 3 years; 5) the period of personology (becoming a person) - from 3 to 5 years; 6) period of differentiation - from 6 to 11 years; 7) puberty and adolescence - from 12 to 18 years.

Literature analysis.

The study of age crises in psychology reveals the multifaceted concept of age, its consequences and psychological constructions around it in the literature on this topic.

Friedler (2012) begins this discourse by critically analyzing the concept of aging and its social constructions. The article outlines aspects specific to the definition of aging, emphasizing the importance of psychological perspectives in mental health contexts for older adults. This key piece lays the groundwork for understanding the implications of the older population and highlights the need for research that informs counseling psychology practice, thereby providing an important foundation for further research.

Building on this, Perrig-Chiello and Perren (2018) examine the biographical transitions experienced during midlife and argue that an individual's life span is defined by a series of interrelated transitions. Their findings reveal important insights into how past experiences shape current well-being and influence perceptions of aging. This article highlights the importance of recognizing stability and variability in life narratives, suggesting that a life course perspective is essential to understanding the psychological adaptations required in later life.

M. Hanna et al., (2018) extend this research to emerging adults, examining stressors and adaptations associated with transitions in this age group. Their scoping review identifies methodologically relevant studies, illuminating how developmental and situational changes influence psychological well-being. This study provides a counterpoint to the themes of aging and adaptation discussed in previous studies by highlighting specific challenges faced by younger populations.

The impact of external events such as the COVID-19 pandemic is addressed by Schlomann et al. (2020), who analyze how negative age stereotypes exacerbate the psychological problems faced by older people during crises. Their research sheds light on the relationship between attitudes toward aging and psychological adjustment, suggesting that negative perceptions can significantly impede well-being. This contribution is crucial in understanding the psychological implications of aging in the contemporary context and societal relationships.

Analysis and Results.

The problem of stratification of youth periods in Russian psychology began to be reflected in the works of great psychologists such as L.S. Vygotsky, P.P. Blonsky, B.G. Ananov. Later, the number of people dealing with this problem increased, therefore, the problem of classification of age periods differs sharply from the point of view of its origin, scientific source, approach to development processes. At present, when thinking about the classification of age periods, it is appropriate to divide the scientific views of scientists into certain groups and reveal their essence. L.S. Vygotsky critically analyzes the theories of psychologists' classification of age periods and divides age periods into the following stages based on mental renewals that create certain development;

1. Infancy crisis.
2. Infancy period - from 2 months to 1 year. One-year crisis.
3. Early childhood - from 1 to 3 years old - crisis of 3 years.
4. Preschool period - from 3 to 7 years - 7 years crisis.
5. School age period - from 8 years to 12 years - 13 years crisis.
6. Puberty (sexual maturity) period - from 14 to 18 years, crisis at 17 years.

If adults take into account the child's new needs and help to create opportunities to meet them, the crisis may not arise. In this, the development of the individual is ensured without crisis and in a peaceful way. In general, psychologists have developed a number of theories of stratification of age periods with a thorough, scientific and methodological basis. Nowadays, they make a great contribution to the illumination of ontogenetic laws and occupy an important place in solving its theoretical and practical problems. However, even so, there is a need to create a theory that can serve to fully illuminate ontogenesis. At each age, some type of activity plays a leadership role. The concept of the leading type of activity is revealed in the works of A.N. Leontev. The leading type of activity is the type of activity that causes significant changes in the child's psyche, mental processes and mental characteristics at a certain age. At every age there is

a need for some kind of activity. For example: the leading type of activity during infancy is direct emotional communication, on the basis of which orientation and sensorimotor-manipulative actions are formed, that is, actions controlled by vision, hearing, muscle-motor sensations, perception. The most important innovation in this age is the need for communication with other people and the formation of a certain emotional relationship with them. The leading type of activity in early childhood is subject-oriented activities. Through it, the child learns actions performed with objects in cooperation with adults. The novelty of this period is the development of speech and visual movement thinking.

In the pre-school age, role-playing games are the leading type of activity. Study activity is the leading type of activity at junior school age. Memory is formed in reading activities, knowledge about subjects and the outside world is acquired. In adolescence, communication serves as leadership. In the period of early adolescence, the leading type of activity is educational and professional activity, in the process of which worldview, professional interests, self-awareness, dreams and ideals are formed.

Therefore, age characteristics are typical for each period. But there are also individual differences within each age group. The reasons for this difference can be different:

1. Conditions of life, work and upbringing.
2. Natural individual differences - typological features of the nervous system.

It is necessary to take into account the psychological and individual psychological characteristics of students in educational work, that is, it is necessary to choose and use the forms, methods and tools of pedagogical work that match the requirements, capabilities, and characteristics of children of this age.

Summary. In summary, youth crises are complex and multifaceted phenomena that are shaped by a number of factors, including life events, relationships, and cultural influences. The study of age crises has provided important insights into human life by highlighting the various challenges and opportunities faced at different stages of life. Although there are several limitations and gaps in the current state of knowledge, future research should aim to address these limitations by conducting studies that examine age crises in different cultural settings. By deepening our understanding of age crises, researchers can provide practitioners with the knowledge and tools needed to support individuals navigating these critical life periods.

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